

ICCM24

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

High performance vitrimer composites manufactured by filament winding

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Vitrimer composites a hybrid class of material

- Vitrimer composites are special because of their polymeric matrix
- Hybrid between thermosets and thermoplastic polymers

Thermoplastics

Fusible et soluble → reshapable and recyclable

Limited mechanical and thermal resistance

Thermosets

High thermal, chemical and mechanical properties → High performance applications

Non-repairable and non-recyclable

Thermoset properties

Thermoplastic properties

Most used chemistries in vitrimer epoxy based composite

• Transesterification

• Disulfide exchange

Vitrimer composites : dynamic properties

Reprocessability

Repairability

Recyclability

Reshapability

weldability

- Mainly lab scale composite production
- Main objective of next years : are vitrimer matrixes compatible with classic composite manufacturing processes ?

Filament winding manufacturing process

Widely used in aerospace, automotive, and energy industry

precise control of **fiber placement and fiber volume fraction**
→ optimized performance

- Material : uncured resin for wet winding, or prepreg continuous fiber : carbon, glass or aramide
- Ideal process to produce cylindrical or spherical components such as pipes or pressure vessels

Pipe winding, not only..

→ Filament winding is a manufacturing process used for many purpose, the only edge is imagination and engineering skills

Filament winding overwrap of third generation deck

Outside filament-wound FRP bridge deck (Feng et al, 2006)

Manufacturing of a flate plate

Manufacturing of an unidirectional plate via automated filament winding

Flat pieces can be produced via filament winding, with higher volume ratio than other manufacturing process

Plate winding : challenges

Porosities in final material and heterogeneities :

macroporosities created between fibers → fiber overlap
Microporosities → bad impregnation

Step A

Step B

Non homogenous parameters through the winding → hypothetic heterogeneities in the final composite part

Filament winding

In filament winding, the matrix plays a crucial role, and specific requirements must be met to ensure effective fiber impregnation

Viscosity as a function of temperature,
 $\omega = 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$, interfer 1 mm, $3^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$

Temperature bath must permit to obtain a viscosity of 1000 mPa.s (scientifically accepted value for good impregnation)
 → $40\text{-}50^\circ\text{C}$

Viscosity stability on isotherms

Chemical stability must be long enough to permit long term experiment (2-3h long)
 → Gel time is compatible with the process

Filament winding Applied parameters

Material : disulfide HP epoxy resin as vitrimer matrix– M55J fibers

Bath temperature : 50°C
Fiber tension : 1bar
Average speed

Composite part : unidirectional plate 0°, 8 plies

Choice on curing procedure has an impact ?
Oven with void bag
Press curing
Autoclave

Curing dependance oven curing

Parameters : Temperature

Moderate cost
easy implementation

Amplitude CT-scan of the cured plate

Microscopic image of the oven cured sample – magnification x50

- bad microscopic structure quality
 - Porosities (majorly macropores due to overlaps), resin pockets due to non repartition of the resin in the plate during curing)
 - Good fiber alignment despite the non homogeneous fiber tension applied through the winding
- Plate winding necessitate compression molding post winding to decrease heterogeneities in the material created during winding

Curing dependance Hot press

Parameters : Temperature, pressure

Moderate cost

Complex implementation

Amplitude CT-scan of the obtained sample

Pressure is applied at 25% of conversion ($\alpha_{gel} = 45\%$) and less different temperature isotherms

Amplitude CT-scan of the obtained sample

Pressure is applied at 5% of conversion and more different temperature isotherms are applied to slowly increase viscosity

The resin distribution is **highly dependent on the parameters applied**, pressure and temperature has to be perfectly controlled as well as resin kinetic to obtain a good internal structure

Curing dependance Autoclave

Parameters : Temperature-
Void -Pressure

High cost
Complex implementation

Monitoring of the curing cycle for
autoclave curing

CT-scan

Good fiber alignment, good structure with homogeneous distribution

Numeric microscope

No porosities or plies overlap, no resin pocket are visible

Objectif E20.X50

0.5 mm

Obtained composite plate
(400*250 mm), UD 0°

Void and pressure help obtaining a very good resin repartition with perfect impregnation of fiber and the absence of porosities

Vf = 68 %

Mechanical properties of autoclave plate

Autoclave is giving best structure, mechanical performance are tested on this material
Tensile and 3 point bending tests are conducted

Stress / strain curve for tensile test

Stress / strain curve for 3 point bending test

	Tensile modulus E (GPa)	Maximum stress σ (MPa)	Maximum strain ϵ (%)	Poisson coefficient
HTG240-V-1/1.2-M55J	308 +/- 2	1495 +/- 35	3.1 +/- 0.1	0.27 +/- 0.01

	Flexural modulus E_f (GPa)	Maximum stress σ (MPa)	Maximum strain ϵ (%)
HTG240-V-1/1.2-M55J	231 +/- 2	755 +/- 26	0.33 +/- 0.01

Reparation process : time and temperature

Stress relaxation experiment for neat vitrimer matrix, $\epsilon = 2\%$

ATG test at 200°C isotherm

Stress relaxation of a 2% strain can occur at 200°C on neat resin after 162s

At 200°C, 1% degradation occurs after 50 min
 → In the reprocessing window of the material

Reparation process - time and pressure influence

Different pressure tested : 1, 3 or 5 MPa
 Different durations : 20 or 40 min

Reparation process
 under heated press

Pressure	20 min	40 min
1 MPa		
3 MPa		
5 MPa		

1 MPa
 3 MPa
 5 MPa

ineffective repair process
 few red spots, suggesting resin migration
 significant improvement

Clear effect of time, at 5 MPa, 40 min helps obtaining a near complete repair.

Reparation process - time and pressure influence

Initial state

1 MPa : resin start migrating, repair is insufficient

3 MPa : Better porosity filling, ply separation reduced

5 MPa : noticeable repair, porosity decrease and homogeneous material obtained

Reparation process - time and pressure influence

X-Ray Tomography of samples repaired for 20 min

Pressure	Porosity (%)
No reparation	29,5%
1MPa	26,4%
3MPa	17,3%
5MPa	4,1%

→ Porosity level is an indicator for resin migration and reparation effectiveness

Reparation on composite plate

DMA study post reparation

3 point bending, transverse direction,
Dydn=01 μ m and frequency = 1Hz

5 MPa shows a great increase in storage modulus E' compared to 1 and 3 MPa

Gap between E' (20min) and E' (40min) increases with pressure. At 1MPa : \downarrow 14%, 3MPa : \downarrow 24% and 5MPa : \downarrow 62%
 Loss mechanical properties with time but unchanged thermal stability

Conclusion

Production of a High-Performance Composite via Filament Winding

- Vitrimer resin successfully adapted to the filament winding process
- Mastery of rheological and kinetic behavior is essential prior to impregnation
- Curing mode significantly influences:
 - Final microstructure
 - Porosity content
 - Composite homogeneity

Advantages of Vitrimer Resin Integration :

- Enables **repair of production defects or scraps**
- Contributes to **porosity reduction**
- Improves **mechanical performance** (e.g., higher storage modulus)
- Does **not affect thermal stability** ($T\alpha$)
- Effects are **amplified under higher pressure**

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